

NATURE AND ADDER STUDY

We are very interested to find out how you feel about nature and adders, a snake that lives in our countryside.

Please tell us about yourself:

Name

Age Gender

School

Class Teacher

Please circle yes or no:

Do you have a pet snake? YES NO

Have you ever seen a snake in real life? YES NO

Have you ever held a snake in real life? YES NO

In which of the following places do you most like to spend your free time? (Circle).

Park Bedroom The woods

Living room The beach Home garden

Other (please say.....)

Instructions: Please read the statement, then circle the appropriate number

1 = completely disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 neither agree nor disagree; 4=agree 5= completely agree

I like to hear different sounds in nature	1	2	3	4	5
I like to see wild flowers in nature	1	2	3	4	5
When I feel sad, I like to go outside and enjoy nature	1	2	3	4	5
Being in the natural environment makes me feel peaceful	1	2	3	4	5
I like gardening	1	2	3	4	5
Collecting rocks and shells is fun	1	2	3	4	5
Being outdoors makes me happy	1	2	3	4	5
I feel sad when wild animals are hurt	1	2	3	4	5
I like to see wild animals living in a natural environment	1	2	3	4	5
I enjoy touching animals and plants	1	2	3	4	5
Taking care of animals is important to me	1	2	3	4	5
Humans are part of the natural world	1	2	3	4	5
People cannot live without plants and animals	1	2	3	4	5
My actions will make the natural world different	1	2	3	4	5
Picking up litter on the ground can help the environment	1	2	3	4	5
People should not change the natural environment	1	2	3	4	5

Instructions: Again, please read the statement, then circle the appropriate number

1=completely disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neither agree nor disagree; 4=agree; 5=completely agree

Seeing an adder in the wild would be very special	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are interesting animals	1	2	3	4	5
I would stay away from where adders live	1	2	3	4	5
It's important to find out more about adders	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are creepy	1	2	3	4	5
If somebody said adders were nearby, I would be worried	1	2	3	4	5
I would watch a TV programme about adders	1	2	3	4	5
I would like to see an adder	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are worth saving	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are beautiful	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are frightening	1	2	3	4	5
Adders need our protection	1	2	3	4	5
I would go into the countryside even if there were adders in it	1	2	3	4	5
I feel worried just thinking about adders	1	2	3	4	5
It would be bad if there were no adders	1	2	3	4	5
Learning more about adders is a good thing	1	2	3	4	5
Adders are important for the natural world	1	2	3	4	5
Adders need looking after	1	2	3	4	5
I get panicky when I think about adders	1	2	3	4	5
You are really lucky if you see an adder	1	2	3	4	5
I would be worried walking in the countryside, if I knew there may be adders around	1	2	3	4	5
I would enjoy watching an adder	1	2	3	4	5
Watching adders on telly would make me feel sick	1	2	3	4	5
We should have adders in our countryside	1	2	3	4	5
I want to know more about adders	1	2	3	4	5

Finally, all of these animals live in the UK (where we live) and are in need of our help. If it was your job to look after them, which **three animals** would you choose to help? Please draw a circle around the three animals you would like to help.

Great Crested Newt

Water Vole

Noctule Bat

Small pearl-bordered fritillary

Dormouse

Adder

Lesser Silver Water Beetle

Sand Lizard

Curlew

THANK YOU SO MUCH FOR YOUR TIME COMPLETING OUR QUESTIONNAIRE!

PLEASE ADD ANY FURTHER COMMENTS HERE IF YOU WISH.